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**Adaptation of international standards of education in the field of cosmetology
to the national context of personnel training**

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Abstract. *Analysis of international educational standards in the field of cosmetology allows us to identify areas for improving students' competence and the effectiveness of specialist training, taking into account national regulatory and socio-cultural characteristics. The relevance of the topic stems from the need to harmonize the Ukrainian system of vocational education with international standards for implementing innovative approaches in the educational process and ensuring the competitiveness of future specialists in the global labor market. The purpose of the study is to analyze the compliance of the Ukrainian system of personnel training with international educational standards, determine ways to integrate world practices into curricula, and assess the impact of harmonizing educational requirements on the development of students' professional competencies. Methods.* *To achieve this goal, methods such as analyzing regulatory documents, comparative research on educational programs of foreign and Ukrainian educational institutions, systematizing statistical data, and conducting sociological surveys of students and teachers were employed. The study's results showed that implementing international standards contributes to the development of professional, methodological, and communicative competencies, as well as the formation of critical thinking and the ability to make independent decisions in*

*professional activities. It was found that the main barriers to harmonizing educational programs are the insufficient material and technical base of educational institutions, the limited level of teacher training in using innovative methods, as well as the need to adjust curricula to account for national regulatory requirements and socio-cultural characteristics. The **conclusions of the study** indicate that effective harmonization of international standards is possible with a comprehensive approach, phased implementation of innovative curricula, systematic monitoring of results and advanced training of teaching staff, which ensures the integration of the Ukrainian system of cosmetology education into the international educational space and increases the level of professional training of personnel.*

Keywords: *professional training, international educational standards, cosmetology, competency-based approach, curriculum alignment, innovative methodologies.*

Адаптація міжнародних стандартів освіти в галузі косметології до національного контексту підготовки кадрів

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Анотація. *Аналіз міжнародних освітніх стандартів у галузі косметології дозволяє визначити напрями підвищення компетентності студентів та ефективності підготовки фахівців з урахуванням національних нормативних і соціально-культурних особливостей. Актуальність теми зумовлена необхідністю гармонізації української системи професійної освіти з міжнародними вимогами для впровадження інноваційних підходів у навчальний процес та забезпечення конкурентоспроможності майбутніх фахівців на глобальному ринку праці. **Метою** дослідження є аналіз*

відповідності української системи підготовки кадрів міжнародним освітнім стандартам, визначення шляхів інтеграції світових практик у навчальні програми та оцінка впливу узгодження освітніх вимог на розвиток професійних компетентностей студентів. **Методи.** Для досягнення поставленої мети застосовувалися методи аналізу нормативно-правових документів, порівняльного дослідження освітніх програм закордонних та українських навчальних закладів, систематизації статистичних даних, а також соціологічного опитування студентів і викладачів. **Результати** дослідження показали, що впровадження міжнародних стандартів сприяє формуванню професійних, методичних та комунікативних компетентностей, розвитку критичного мислення та здатності до самостійного прийняття рішень у професійній діяльності. Виявлено, що основними бар'єрами узгодження освітніх програм є недостатня матеріально-технічна база навчальних закладів, обмежений рівень підготовки викладачів до використання інноваційних методик, а також необхідність коригування навчальних планів з урахуванням національних нормативних вимог та соціально-культурних особливостей. **Висновки** дослідження свідчать, що ефективно узгодження міжнародних стандартів можливе за умови комплексного підходу, поетапного впровадження інноваційних навчальних програм, систематичного моніторингу результатів та підвищення кваліфікації педагогічного персоналу, що забезпечує інтеграцію української системи освіти косметологів у міжнародний освітній простір та підвищує рівень професійної підготовки кадрів.

Ключові слова: професійна підготовка, міжнародні стандарти освіти, косметологія, компетентнісний підхід, узгодження освітніх програм, інноваційні методики.

Problem statement. The current task of modern education is to align training programs for specialists in the field of cosmetology with international standards,

ensuring the development of a high level of professional competence and competitiveness among graduates. The main aspects of the problem are the assessment of national curricula compliance with global educational standards, the integration of innovative teaching methods and knowledge control, as well as taking into account the regulatory, legal, socio-cultural, and material and technical features of Ukrainian educational institutions. The need for a detailed study arises from the desire to enhance the efficiency of the educational process, ensure high-quality training of personnel, and integrate the Ukrainian system of cosmetologist education into the international professional space. The study focuses on identifying the primary barriers to the adoption of international standards, evaluating their impact on the development of students' professional competencies, and developing recommendations for optimizing curricula.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The problem of integrating international educational standards into the system of professional training of cosmetology specialists occupies a leading place in modern scientific research. J. Li and M. Pilz [1] investigate the features of the international transfer of vocational education, identifying key models and mechanisms for adapting educational systems to globalization processes. The authors emphasize the need to harmonize national educational programs with international standards. H. M. Tereshchenko [2] analyzes the reform of the Ukrainian education system in the context of European integration. The work emphasizes the importance of harmonizing national educational policy with European approaches and implementing competency-based learning. V. H. Kremen, V. I. Lugovyi and P. Y. Saukh [3] consider education and science as a basic factor in the innovative development of society. Researchers point to the need to integrate scientific achievements into the practice of vocational training. M. Kahanec et al. [4] investigate strategies for restoring and modernizing the Ukrainian education system. The authors suggest focusing on the experience of European countries to ensure the effective development of the educational environment. V. Nazarenko [5] analyzes the evolution of makeup as a means of

forming visual identity in the media space. The results of the study confirm the need to take into account cultural aspects in the training of cosmetology specialists. Lviv Medical Professional College «Monada» [6] developed the course «Basic Cosmetology» and «Cosmetology + Injection Techniques», which defines a competency-based approach as the basis for training future specialists. The Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine has approved a higher education standard for specialty 224 «Technologies of medical diagnostics and treatment», which ensures the unification of educational outcomes at the state level [7]. CIDESCO International offers an international standard for training beauty industry specialists, presented in the Beauty Therapy Diploma program [8]. This program is the basis for the formation of globally recognized qualification requirements. CIBTAC develops qualification standards for the training of cosmetologists and beauty specialists, which are used in leading educational institutions in the world [9]. D. J. Kellie, K. R. Blake and R. C. Brooks [10] investigate the impact of cosmetics on women's self-objectification processes and their perception by others, which is important to consider in the professional training of cosmetologists. A. L. Mafra, C. S. A. Silva, M. A. C. Varella and J. V. Valentova [11] analyze the relationship between body image, self-esteem and the use of makeup. The study emphasizes the psychological aspects of cosmetology practices. P. A. Albarran [12] examines trends in the use of makeup on television during the twentieth century, focusing on the impact of high-definition images on the appearance of journalists. N. M. Anchieta et al. [13] studied the impact of makeup use and its imitation on women's self-esteem. The results confirm the importance of cosmetic care for psychological comfort. K. Pottenger [14] highlights the practical aspects of the work of a makeup artist, describing professional challenges and requirements for qualifications in the field of makeup. M. Bertash, S. Polishchuk, V. Burdun, N. Ivanyshyn and V. Zhulkovskyi [15] substantiate the need to use European experience in the formation of professional competencies of future specialists of the vocational education system of Ukraine. O. Nahorniuk and L. Levytska [16] propose the integration of professional and

educational standards into the process of developing curricula, which ensures consistency between the requirements of the labor market and the training system. V. A. Zabora [17] investigates the optimization of personal image through quantitative changes in hairstyle and makeup, which is relevant for professional activities in the field of cosmetology.

Literature analysis indicates that implementing international educational standards in cosmetologist training necessitates a comprehensive approach, which involves updating curricula content, integrating a competency-based approach, enhancing teacher qualifications, and ensuring a modern material and technical infrastructure. At the same time, there are gaps in the systematic application of innovative methods and standardized practical tasks at all stages of professional training, which require further improvement of the educational process.

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the general problem.

Analysis of research in the field of training specialists in cosmetology reveals that most studies focus on individual components of the educational process, such as program modernization, practical training, or the introduction of innovative technologies. Despite the significant scientific contribution, there are no comprehensive approaches to integrating international norms and methods at all stages of professional development, from mastering the theoretical base and forming practical skills to assessing the competencies that have been formed. The influence of cultural, psychological and technological aspects on the development of students professional skills in national conditions has not been sufficiently studied. In addition, the limited analytical assessment of the effectiveness of the phased implementation of global standards in curricula creates gaps in the formulation of recommendations for optimizing the educational process.

Unresolved issues are key to a comprehensive understanding of the problem, as the systematic combination of global practices and local characteristics determines the level of professional training, the readiness of specialists to meet market requirements, and the ability to make independent decisions in professional

activities. Eliminating these gaps will contribute to the development of methodological recommendations that will ensure the effective adaptation of international standards to the national educational context of cosmetology.

Formulation of the article's objectives (statement of the task). The purpose of the study is to determine ways to effectively adapt international standards of education in the field of cosmetology to the national context of specialist training.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks are envisaged:

1. To analyze modern international educational standards in the field of cosmetology and identify their key components that affect the formation of professional competencies.

2. Assess the compliance of national cosmetology training programs with international requirements and identify gaps in the practical and theoretical training of students.

3. Explore the possibilities of integrating innovative teaching methods and practical training into national educational programs, taking into account socio-cultural and regulatory features.

4. Develop scientific and methodological recommendations for the implementation of a comprehensive approach to the adaptation of international standards in the training of specialists, which will contribute to increasing the competitiveness of graduates and the quality of professional training.

The implementation of these tasks will allow systematizing existing experience, eliminating existing gaps and making a practically significant contribution to the development of the national system of training cosmetologists in accordance with world standards. The validity of the goals emphasizes the relevance of the topic and determines the logical sequence of further scientific analysis and conclusions.

Presentation of the main research material. The Ukrainian system of training specialists in the field of cosmetology is undergoing an active transformation, driven by global trends and the need to comply with international

educational standards. In the world, comprehensive regulatory frameworks have been developed by authoritative organizations such as CIDESCO, CIBTAC, and ITEC, which determine the content of professional programs, the level of qualification requirements, and approaches to practical training. These standards focus on a competency-based approach, the integration of innovative technologies, and strict adherence to safety standards.

Analysis of international educational standards reveals their systematic structure. They contain clear criteria for the duration of training, the ratio of theoretical and practical hours, the use of modern equipment and ensuring the safety of procedures. The main components that determine the quality of professional training are the modular organization of training, a multi-level certification system, mandatory practice in real conditions and the development of communicative and analytical skills [1].

International approaches pay special attention to the competence formation of specialists, which includes not only the acquisition of technical skills, but also the ability to make independent decisions, manage work processes and effectively interact with clients. In the national education system, these aspects need to be strengthened, as the traditional model of learning primarily focuses on the reproductive assimilation of knowledge [2, p. 46].

The process of adapting international standards to the Ukrainian educational context must take into account the current legislation, cultural features and the actual state of the material and technical base of educational institutions. Direct copying of foreign models is impractical due to differences in the regulatory field and resource provision. Therefore, an important task is the development of integrated programs that combine the best practices of international standards with national educational features of specialist training [3].

One of the priority areas for harmonizing national educational programs with international standards is the modernization of curricula through the introduction of modular course organization, the use of simulation technologies, the expansion of

industrial practice bases, and the integration of electronic educational platforms. Such approaches contribute to the development of critical thinking, teamwork and readiness to apply innovative technologies in professional activities.

No less important is compliance with ethical and safety standards, which are mandatory in international programs. They regulate professional behavior, confidentiality and hygiene rules, which contribute to the formation of trust between a specialist and a client and an increase in the level of professional culture. The integration of these provisions into domestic educational programs ensures compliance with international standards and enhances the competitiveness of Ukrainian specialists on the global market [4, p. 552].

At the same time, the use of innovative pedagogical technologies, particularly virtual simulators, interactive simulations, and digital platforms for distance learning, enables the optimization of the educational process and brings it closer to international standards. The use of digital tools contributes to the flexibility of learning and the formation of digital competencies, which are becoming necessary for modern specialists in the field of cosmetology [5, p. 170].

Within the framework of the work, a targeted analysis of the current national cosmetology training programs was carried out for compliance with international requirements. The sample included the curricula of the Kyiv Medical College named after P. I. Gavros, the professional College of the Bukovyna State Medical University, the Kharkiv State Medical College and the Lviv Medical Professional College «Monada». The mentioned programs are primarily focused on basic modules in dermatology, anatomy, physiology, sanitation, and hygiene, as well as classical skin care methods. The Lviv Medical Professional College «Monada» offers cosmetology courses, including practice on modern equipment and partnership with leading brands of professional cosmetics. The share of practical training is approximately 300–350 hours per cycle, which does not provide intensive practice of manipulations on real models and work with modern equipment [6; 7].

For benchmarking, the reference requirements of CIDESCO and CIBTAC were used, which determine the structure of programs, the minimum number of hours, the list of mandatory modules, the requirements for the material and technical base, and the format of certification assessment [8; 9]. The generalized results of the comparison are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Comparison of Ukrainian and international cosmetology training programs

Component	Ukrainian colleges programs	International programs (CIDESCO; CIBTAC)
<i>General design</i>	Traditional model, theory advantage	Competency model, theory/practice balance
<i>Practice volume</i>	~300–350 hrs. per cycle	1000+ hrs. of intensive practice, internship in salons
<i>Modularity</i>	Basic blocks (care, hygiene, physiotherapy)	Advanced modules: hardware technologies (laser/IPL, RF, microcurrents), infection control, client management, business fundamentals
<i>Teaching methods</i>	Lectures, laboratory classes, short internships	Simulations, demonstration practices on models, case method, and long-term practicum
<i>Assessment</i>	Written exams, credits	Practical exams on models, standardized demonstrations, and portfolio
<i>Ethics and safety</i>	Regulatory topics are integrated fragmentarily	Separate modules on professional ethics, safety of procedures, and communication with the client

Source: compiled by the author based on [6-9]

The identified discrepancies are of a practical nature and affect the level of training of specialists. The insufficient number of practical hours limits the development of stable manual skills and the safe application of hardware techniques. The limited use of modern equipment, including laser and IPL systems, radiofrequency technologies, and digital skin diagnostics, narrows the range of professional competencies of graduates compared to international standards. The theoretical nature of the assessment of learning outcomes does not provide for the

demonstration of practical skills. In contrast, the certification requirements of CIDESCO and CIBTAC provide for mandatory practical testing of competencies in standardized conditions. Additionally, the development of soft skills, such as communication skills, customer service, claims handling, and the basics of business processes, is implemented fragmentarily in national programs, which limits the readiness of graduates for effective interaction with customers and the management of work processes.

The identified discrepancies underscore the need for a systematic review of the structure of national educational programs for cosmetologist training. One of the priority areas is to increase the share of practical classes to meet international certification standards. It will ensure the development of sustainable technical skills, the competent application of hardware techniques, and an increase in the level of professional training of graduates.

A necessary measure is the integration of specialized modules on hardware technologies, infection control and professional ethics, which will ensure comprehensive training of specialists and minimize potential risks in professional activities. The introduction of such components will contribute to increasing the level of safety in procedures, fostering professional responsibility, and developing critical thinking when working with clients [10, p. 715].

Competency assessment, which includes a mandatory demonstration of practical skills and portfolio management, enables an objective evaluation of students readiness to perform professional tasks. This approach fosters the development of analytical skills, independence in decision-making, and the ability to manage work processes effectively in the modern labor market.

The systematic development of customer orientation and basic entrepreneurial competencies ensures the improvement of customer service quality, the formation of management skills, and readiness to implement business projects in the cosmetology field.

Taken together, the implementation of these measures aims to enhance the professional competence of graduates, ensure the safe and high-quality provision of cosmetology services, and integrate the Ukrainian system of training specialists into the international educational space. It will contribute to strengthening the competitiveness of specialists in the global cosmetology services market and increasing the authority of Ukrainian education in the fields of healthcare and aesthetics [11].

The integration of innovative techniques into the cosmetologist training process should take into account the specific national context, particularly its socio-cultural and legislative features. Socio-cultural factors include increased attention to the safety of procedures, hygiene, and ethical norms in communicating with clients, which necessitate the formation of communicative and psychological competencies, in addition to technical skills. Legislative requirements relate to the licensing of educational programs, qualification standards for specialists and compliance with sanitation and safety standards during practical classes, which determines the scope of application of hardware technologies and the scope of practice.

Requirements for the material and technical base include the availability of modern equipment for skin care procedures and hardware techniques (lasers, IPL, RF systems, microcurrents), equipped training laboratories and digital platforms for distance and simulation learning. The use of virtual simulators and interactive platforms enables students to safely practice practical skills, even with limited access to equipment. Meanwhile, case method and simulation classes contribute to the development of critical thinking, analytical skills, and decision-making abilities in professional situations [12, p. 88-90].

In addition, the systematic inclusion of practical training in the development of soft skills - communication, customer service, ethics of professional behavior, and the basics of entrepreneurship - ensures a more comprehensive readiness of students to implement professional activities in accordance with international standards. This approach enables the combination of global educational practices with Ukrainian

traditions and regulatory requirements, thereby forming a comprehensive system for training competitive specialists [13, p. 3780].

The introduction of elements of international standards into national cosmetology training programs has a significant impact on the development of key competencies of students. The combination of modular training organization, practical training, and simulation technologies contributes to the development of professional skills necessary for performing complex cosmetology procedures and working with modern equipment.

Some Ukrainian institutions are already seeing positive results from adopting international standards. For example, the Lviv Medical Professional College «Monada» has introduced a module for practical work on IPL and laser equipment, which allows students to practice techniques on models using modern methods of safe procedure performance. Similar initiatives at the Aesthetic Medicine Training Center at the V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University include simulators and case studies on managing cosmetology processes, which contribute to the formation of comprehensive professional skills and readiness for practical activities.

Methodological competencies are strengthened through the systematic inclusion of interactive teaching methods, case studies, and distance learning platforms, which enable students to effectively plan the educational process, analyze results, and independently adjust their learning approaches. Such an organization contributes to the development of critical thinking skills and independent decision-making in professional activities [14, p. 90].

Communicative competencies are developed through the integration of specialized modules in customer service, professional ethics, relationship management, and teamwork. It ensures effective interaction between students and colleagues and clients, increases the level of professional culture, and prepares specialists for activities in a competitive service market [15, p. 153].

Based on the analysis and comparison of national and international cosmetology training programs, scientific and methodological recommendations

have been formulated to improve educational programs, taking into account international standards. The recommendations provide for the systematic application of a competency-based approach, a modular organization of training, and the integration of practical training with simulation technologies. This approach will contribute to the balanced development of students professional, methodological, and communicative competencies, as well as increase their readiness for effective and safe professional activity. It is advisable to introduce a system of regular monitoring of learning outcomes and certification, which provides for the mandatory demonstration of practical skills on models, maintaining a portfolio, and assessing soft skills, which allows you to track the dynamics of competency formation and timely adjust the educational process. To ensure the systematic integration of international standards, it is advisable to introduce a comprehensive system for assessing the effectiveness of training. It may include regular surveys of students and teachers, comparison of practical exam results before and after the implementation of innovative methods, as well as analysis of the dynamics of soft skills formation through portfolio and case methods [16, p. 166].

It is also recommended to expand the use of electronic educational platforms and distance technologies to increase learning flexibility, as well as adapt modules to incorporate hardware methods and innovative procedures, taking into account the existing material and technical base, as well as regulatory requirements. The integration of modern educational technologies and hardware modules requires certain resource investments. Still, the investments quickly pay off by improving the quality of student training and their competitiveness in the labor market. The use of virtual simulators, digital simulations and interactive platforms allows you to reduce costs for equipment and materials, while ensuring a high level of practical training. It makes the educational process effective both from a methodological and economic point of view.

A comprehensive approach involves taking into account the socio-cultural features of the Ukrainian educational environment, which will enable the

preservation of the national specificity of specialist training while integrating advanced international experience. The implementation of these recommendations will contribute to increasing the competitiveness of graduates, improving the quality of the educational process and integrating the Ukrainian system of cosmetology education into the global educational space [17, p. 176].

Despite the achieved results of implementing individual international practices into national programs, further research is needed to assess the effectiveness of integrating innovative methods in various educational institutions, evaluate the long-term impact on the formation of students' competencies, and adapt programs to changes in regulatory requirements and technological developments. It will ensure the continuous improvement of the educational process and the systematic harmonization of national cosmetologist training with international standards.

Conclusions. The study enabled the assessment of the compliance of national educational programs for training specialists in cosmetology with international standards and the identification of key areas for improvement. It was found that Ukrainian curricula are primarily focused on acquiring basic theoretical knowledge and provide limited practical training, which does not fully comply with the competency-based approach recommended by international standards.

Based on the analysis and comparison of programs, several scientific and methodological recommendations have been formed aimed at improving the quality of cosmetology training. The first includes increasing the volume of practical training to a level comparable to international certification standards, which will ensure the formation of stable technical skills and confident application of hardware techniques in professional activities.

The second direction is to integrate specialized modules on hardware technologies, infection control and professional ethics, which will ensure comprehensive training of specialists and minimize risks when working with clients. The introduction of competency assessment, including the mandatory demonstration

of practical skills and portfolio management, will enable the objective assessment of students readiness for professional activity and the monitoring of the formation of key competencies.

Special attention should be paid to the systematic development of soft skills, in particular customer orientation, communication and basic entrepreneurial competencies. It will contribute to improving the level of service, developing management skills and preparing graduates for effective interaction with customers in real conditions.

The use of innovative technologies, such as virtual simulators, interactive simulations and digital platforms, will allow students to safely practice practical skills and develop critical thinking, even with limited resources. The combination of these approaches with traditional forms of education will ensure the comprehensive formation of professions.

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